

Entropy Production and the Role of Momentum

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The first law of thermodynamics, $dE = TdS - PdV$ (in one form), focuses on energy (dE), not momentum. The second law notes how entropy remains constant or increases if work is not done on the system. This again seems to focus on an energy perspective. For example, if one has a gas at a certain temperature, there is a certain entropy. In terms of energy, one might ask: Why cannot one harness this energy into a collective mode of the system? One such collective mode might be translation, but converting thermal energy into kinetic energy would violate conservation of momentum.

We suggest that a similar idea linked to momentum is present in the example of an accelerating charge. The E (electric) and B (magnetic) fields of an accelerating charge field have no temperature. The charge system has an overall mass and it may be viewed as having a v (velocity) and acceleration dv/dt . The Newtonian picture is that at any dx , an object has a center-of-mass velocity, but is also accelerating. Newtonian mechanics is considered to be consistent with Maxwell's em equations. Thus, at each dx , there should be pieces of the E and B field which match that of a charged distribution moving at constant v , i.e. these pieces only depend on v and not dv/dt . The question becomes: May there be other pieces and if so, would they be part of the charge system? Based on the idea of momentum, the charge system (including bound E and B fields) must be associated with a momentum linked to v . This suggests that any extra pieces of the E and B fields are no longer associated with the charged system and represent entropy production (e.g. radiated photons).

Extra pieces of E and B necessarily appear due to the use of retarded time, thus an accelerating charge seems to be an example in which some work being done on the charged system must necessarily go into entropy production, it cannot all be converted into kinetic energy (including energy in E and B pieces still considered to be bound to the charge). We suggest that this is an alternative to the Carnot engine for showing the presence of entropy in nature.

Thermodynamics and a Focus on Energy not Momentum

The first law of thermodynamics, written in a simple form, is:

$dE = TdS - PdV$ where E is energy, T temperature, S entropy, P pressure and V volume ((1))

Momentum does not appear anywhere in this equation.

Similarly, the second law of thermodynamics states that a system may retain or increase its entropy, unless work is applied. TS has units of energy and one focuses on energy, not momentum. This often leads to the idea of collective energy being distributed to thermal degrees of freedom, but not vice versa, or work not being able to be completely into useful (collective) energy. In turn, this is linked with the idea of an arrow of time.

In particular, if one had a gas at rest with a certain temperature, using energy considerations alone, one might ask why one could not have this thermal energy converted into collective

energy. One immediate example would involve thermal energy being converted into overall kinetic energy of the system, which violates the second law of thermodynamics. This scenario, however, also violates momentum conservation. Similarly, a sound wave moving in one direction which bounces off the container wall would seem to violate momentum conservation because it has net momentum. If one had two sound waves, one with p vector and the other with $-p$ vector, overall momentum would be zero, but if these were created at different positions, this would seem to violate local momentum conservation at each position, because net momentum at each position is initially 0 and the two positions do not communicate instantaneously. In other words, these two sound waves at different points would not be generated spontaneously. Thus, we argue that momentum conservation seems to be important in the case of thermal degrees of freedom (i.e. entropic degrees of freedom) versus collective ones.

We try to apply these ideas to the case of an accelerating charge distribution.

Entropy Production, Momentum and an Accelerating Charge System

If one considers the case of a charge system moving at constant v , it should have an overall mass (including mass energy in the E electric and B magnetic fields) and behave like a Newtonian object. In particular, Newtonian mechanics is compatible with Maxwell's em equations in terms of the charge system and "bound" E and B fields. These bound E and B fields are ones which behave as: $E(v)$, $B(v)$, where v is velocity.

According to Newtonian mechanics, a particle with its center-of-mass in dx , has a velocity $v(x)$ and may or may not be accelerating. As a result, if one considers the case of an accelerating charge system, one may expect a priori that there exist pieces of the E and B fields which match $E(v)$ and $B(v)$ for a constant velocity.

Some questions are: Are there other pieces of E and B , other than $E(v)$ and $B(v)$? If so, why would these not be part of the charge system? If they are not part of the charge system, of what are they part?

To answer the first question, we consider the idea of momentum. According to Newtonian mechanics, a charged particle system at dx must have momentum associated with $v(x)$, even if it is accelerating. This means that only $E(v)$ and $B(v)$ may be part of this momentum. The problem is that there are other pieces of E and B (other than $E(v)$ and $B(v)$), due to retarded time which introduces the notion of a dipole momentum which may exhibit both velocity and acceleration. These extra E and B pieces may not be included as part of the charge system on momentum grounds and must be part of something else.

As a result, work done accelerating the charge particle system cannot be entirely converted into kinetic energy of the charge system and one sees the ideas of thermodynamics/entropy emerge. As a result, if one considers the charge distribution the main part of the system (in terms of rest mass energy), then some em energy is leaving this system which may be considered to be entropic. It may be shown that this em energy is a direct consequence of retarded time which introduces internal degrees of freedom because each piece of charge density sends a signal to a fixed measurement point at a different time, thus breaking the notion of complete kinetic collectivity if acceleration exists in the system. The reason for this is that an expression for E (and also B) contains acceleration terms of a dipole moment, while they should

simply contain $E(v)$ and $B(v)$ if they describe momentum associated with v while the particle has v at dx and some time.

We next consider the details which lead to these results using (1).

First, retarded time is given by:

$$t \rightarrow t - R/c \text{ where } R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'| \quad ((2))$$

where c is the speed of light in a vacuum. \mathbf{r} vector is measured from a fixed origin and \mathbf{r}' to a measurement point at time t , and \mathbf{r}' is measured from the origin to a piece of charge. Breaking a charge into pieces indicates internal degrees of freedom, but that does not mean that they gain independence as in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. For example, a moving object has many molecules (degrees of freedom), but in terms of translation these all move with the same v giving the sense of collectivity.

Each piece of charge sends a signal (traveling at c) to the measurement point at different times, i.e. namely at the retarded time ((2)). It will be shown that this ultimately leads to dipole moment terms and d/dt partial dipole moment terms evaluated at $(t-R/c)$ in the electrostatic potential. E has the sense of a force and so the $-\text{grad } \phi$ piece of E may actually act on a retarded time component yielding d/dt dp/dt partial for the original dp/dt piece = $q v$. Thus, acceleration appears in a piece of E , which is not problematic from the point of view of E serving as a force, but is problematic if E is part of a self-energy which is supposed to have a momentum which depends only on v , not on dv/dt . (For example, the kinetic energy of an accelerating particle depends on $.5mvv$ non-relativistically and not on dv/dt .)

To proceed, following (1), one may write:

$$R \approx r - \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / r \text{ and } 1/R \approx 1/r + (1/(r^2)) \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / r + \dots ((3))$$

Next: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and $B = \text{grad } \times A$ ((4)) where:

$$\phi = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \int dv' \text{ charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t - \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / r) / R \quad ((5a)) \text{ and}$$

$$A = \mu_0/(4\pi) \int dv' J(\mathbf{r}', t - \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / r) / \{ r - (\mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / r) \} \quad ((5b))$$

We focus here only on ϕ and the piece of E from $-\text{grad } \phi$, but our conclusions may be extended to all terms in ((5a)) and ((5b)), and ((4)).

$$\text{Charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t - \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / r) = \text{charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t - r/c)$$

$$+ \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / (cr) \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial charge density (at } \mathbf{r}', t - r/c) + \dots$$

Thus:

$$\phi = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left\{ \frac{q}{r} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \frac{d\mathbf{p}(t-r/c)}{dt} \frac{1}{r^3} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathbf{p}}{\partial \mathbf{r}} \frac{1}{r^2} + \dots \right\} \quad (6)$$

Here $\mathbf{p} = \int d\mathbf{v}' \rho'(\mathbf{r}', t-r/c)$, the dipole moment ((7))

For a point charge moving in the x direction, $\mathbf{p} = qx'$ and $\frac{dp}{dt}(at t-r/c) = qv (at t-r/c)$. ((8))

Thus, ϕ contains the presence of v which is fine as long as $-\text{grad}$ does not change v to dv/dt . In the case of constant motion, v is a constant and grad does not act on a constant. In the case of acceleration, however,

$$-\text{grad} \rightarrow \frac{d}{dt} f(t-r/c) \frac{1}{c} \quad (9)$$

If f is proportional to $v(t)$, then dv/dt is acceleration.

This immediately implies that E , in addition to having the usual v dependent terms of constant v motion, also has terms with dv/dt . This means there is acceleration not linked with v . This violates Newtonian mechanics for an accelerating object and so these pieces of E and B cannot be part of the charge system any longer. They accelerate with dv/dt and move off on their own as entropic radiation.

In particular, the acceleration term from $-\text{grad} \phi$ is: $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{r \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} (at t-r/c)}{r^3}$ ((10))

(1) shows that the $-\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial contribution is: $-\frac{u_0}{4\pi r} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dp}{dt} (at t-r/c)$ ((11))
Both terms drop as $1/r$ while usual fields associated with a point charge drop as $1/r^2$.

We noted that a Newtonian object has momentum and also energy. For the fields:

$$\text{Energy density} = \frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} B \cdot B \quad \text{and} \quad \text{momentum density} = \text{constant } E \times B \quad (12)$$

Thus, $E(v)$ and $B(v)$ pieces contribute the energy and momentum still associated with the charge system, while

Energy density and momentum density using E and B pieces containing acceleration represent entropic radiation. One may integrate densities over volume. If one uses the Poynting vector conservation equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial (energy density)} + \text{grad dot (momentum density)} = 0 \quad (13)$$

then $\text{grad dot } (E \times B)$ becomes a surface area integral with $E \times B$ dot surface area normal vector. The surface area goes as $1/r^2$ while the acceleration pieces E and B both go as $1/r$ so $r^2/r^2 = \text{constant}$ and radiation is actually escaping from the charge system. This radiation has no charge, but does have E and B pieces.

Entropic Interpretation

We suggest that the accelerating charge example is one which shows a system in which not all work applied to the system may be converted into kinetic energy. Some of it must necessarily go into the radiated photons, i.e. entropy. As a result, the accelerating charge picture, which was known in the late 1800s, is an example of the idea of a system which must produce entropy and one cannot convert all work energy into collective kinetic energy. (One does not need to only examine the Carnot cycle of a system which has a less than 100% efficiency and introduces entropic notions, i.e. entropy production.)

Conclusion

The idea of the Carnot engine shows that one cannot always obtain useful collective energy, i.e. that sometimes entropic energy/entropy must also be produced.

We suggest here that momentum conservation helps to sometimes explain why entropic degrees of freedom associated with heat cannot convert themselves into collective motion because this would imply a violation of conservation of momentum.

We extend the idea of momentum to an accelerating charge system which should be compatible with both Newtonian mechanics and Maxwell's em laws. According to Newtonian mechanics, the charge system should have a $v(x)$ at a dx even if it is accelerating. As a result, only $E(v)$ electric field and $B(v)$ magnetic field terms may be part of the charge system. Maxwell's em equations, using reduced time, however, produce E and B terms which depend on dv/dt , acceleration. Thus, these are no longer part of the charge system and some of the work done to accelerate the charge system with its bound $E(v), B(v)$ pieces is lost due to the $E(dv/dt), B(dv/dt)$ pieces, i.e to entropy production. Thus, we argue that in addition to a Carnot cycle, an accelerating charge system which radiates also demonstrates the idea of spontaneous entropy production in nature, an idea which does not usually appear in Newtonian mechanics unless one introduces friction.

References

1. Reit, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison Wiley 1981)